

Doudenal Diverticulum Revealed by an Episode of Acute Pancreatitis: A Case Study

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Abstract

Duodenal diverticulum is a common anatomical finding that is usually asymptomatic but may occasionally cause biliopancreatic complications, including acute pancreatitis. We report the case of a 48-year-old patient who was initially operated for gallbladder sludge and underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Postoperatively, she developed recurrent epigastric pain associated with elevated serum lipase levels. Computed tomography confirmed mild acute pancreatitis (Balthazar stage A). Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography and contrast-enhanced computed tomography after oral contrast ingestion revealed a small duodenal diverticulum in close contact with the second portion of the duodenum and the common bile duct, confirming the diagnosis. Conservative management resulted in a favorable outcome. This case emphasizes the importance of considering duodenal diverticulum as a rare etiology of acute pancreatitis when common causes are excluded.

Introduction

Duodenal diverticulum (DD) is defined as a protrusion of the digestive mucosa and submucosa through the muscular wall of the duodenum [1]. The exact etiology is not clear ; however, it might be the end result of disordered duodenal motility [2]. Advancing age, progressive weakening of intestinal smooth muscles and increase in intraduodenal pressure may all encourage the outpouching of the duodenum. The majority of duodenal diverticula are asymptomatic. Clinical presentation may be characterized by non-specific abdominal symptoms. However, complications, such as haemorrhage, diverticulitis, jaundice, cholangitis, pancreatitis or even perforation, are responsible for clinical manifestations in most cases [2,3].

Here, we summarize the case of a patient with recurrent epigastric pain, revealing a duodenal diverticulum responsible for an episode of acute pancreatitis.

Case Presentation

A 48 year old patient with a history of a cesarean section 14 years ago, presented intense severe

abdominal pain in the epigastrium and right hypochondrium, radiating to the right shoulder, associated with bilious vomiting, without jaundice, fever or any alteration in the patient's general condition. Clinical examination found right hypochondrium tenderness. An abdominal ultrasound shows non-distended gallbladder with sludge, and the biological tests, including lipasemia, transaminases, bilirubin, gamma GT, and alkaline phosphatases, were normal.

The patient underwent laparoscopic surgery. The exploration revealed a non-distended gallbladder with a thin wall, as well as an angioma in segment IV of the liver. A cholecystectomy with subhepatic drainage using a Redon drain was performed.

The postoperative period was marked by recurrent epigastric pain on postoperative day 1, as well external biliary fistula drained by the subhepatic drain. There were no alarming signs on postoperative abdominal ultrasound, and lipasemia was within normal range. She was discharged on postoperative day 5 with the drain remaining in place, and an average amount of collected bile varying from 60 mL to 80 mL per day, until

More Information

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postoperative day 28, when it ceased to collect any output and was therefore removed.

The patient did not experience any symptoms after the drain removal. However, on postoperative day 44, she reported a sudden onset of sharp epigastric pain radiating to the back, accompanied by nausea but without vomiting, jaundice, or fever.

The clinical examination on admission revealed isolated epigastric tenderness. Laboratory tests revealed lipasemia at 163 U/L (three times the normal value), with CRP at 11.2 mg/L, hemoglobin at 14.1 g/dl, and white blood cells at 10520 elements/mm³. The hepatic tests were within normal range, except for elevated gamma glutamyl transferase at 213 U/L. The rest of the tests, particularly the renal, lipidic and hydroelectrolytic tests, were normal.

Consequently, the diagnosis of pancreatitis was confirmed, with no signs of systemic inflammatory response syndrome and a BISAP score of 0/5. The patient was hospitalized, placed on digestive rest, with parenteral nutrition, analgesics, and omeprazole 40 mg twice a day.

CT-scan was performed, showing a Balthazar stage A pancreatitis (Fig.1).

Figure 1: CT Images of Our Patient Showing a Normal-Appearing Pancreas (Stage A Pancreatitis)

The imaging was completed by a magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography confirming the diagnosis of duodenal diverticulum appearing as a small, roughly oval fluid-filled formation behind the head of the pancreas, in close contact with D2 on the outside and in close contact with the common bile duct, with a persistent separating border, measuring approximately 10 x 7 mm. The formation does not enhance after injection.

The formation was better explored on CT scan : it appeared hypodense, with a digestive-like wall. Its content presented the same density as the duodenum's, and contained an air bubble. After ingestion of Gastrografin, passage of the contrast inside

the formation is noted, indicating communication with the duodenum (Fig.2).

In addition, the MRI also shows a pancreas of normal size with no surrounding fat infiltration and no peripancreatic collection. No lithiasis and no dilation of intrahepatic or extrahepatic bile ducts, or Wirsung duct were noticed.

Moreover, simple hepatic cysts were found on the MRI, involving segments II, IV, VI, and VII, with the largest located in segment VI measuring 8x7 mm (Fig.3).

Figure 2: Images from the CT-Scan with Gastrografin Ingestion of Our Patient Demonstrating the Duodenal Diverticulum (Arrow)

Figure 3: Cholangiopancreatic MRI Images of Our Patient Demonstrating the Biliary Cysts (Arrows)

Discussion

First described by Chomel in 1710 [4], duodenal diverticulum (DD) is a protrusion of the digestive mucosa and submucosa through the muscular wall of the duodenum [9]. They are caused by duodenal hyperpressure, which occurs opposite the embryological line of fusion between the ventral and dorsal parts of the pancreas [1,9], which usually makes in an acquired lesion [5].

The prevalence of duodenal diverticulum is correlated with increasing age, with an average of 64 years in the case series of Thorson et al. [3,6].

The duodenum is the second most common site of gastro-intestinal diverticulum formation after the colon, found in up to 22% of autopsies and endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatographies (ERCP). In 62% of cases, DD is situated in the second portion of the duodenum along the pancreatic and mesenteric border, commonly within 2.5 cm of the ampulla of Vater (D2), usually in close proximity to the papilla. In another 30% of cases, DD lies in the third portion of the duodenum (D3), and in 8% of cases in the fourth portion of the duodenum (D4) [3,5,7].

Two types of DD can be described:

Extraluminal duodenal diverticula (90%): is essentially a herniation of the mucosa and submucosa through a defect in the muscular wall of the duodenum, occurring due to a combination of intraluminal pressure and an intrinsic weakness of the muscular wall [10]. Incidence ranges from 6 to 20% in autopsy and endoscopic series, and incidence increases with age. There is no sexual predominance. A relationship between juxtapaillary DD and the incidence of choledocholithiasis has been demonstrated in multiple series. These studies showed that the stones removed from the common bile duct were mainly pigment stones, suggesting primary intraductal stone formation due to stasis rather than passage of gallbladder stones [10].

Intraluminal duodenal diverticula: are of congenital origin. They present as a saccular protrusion of the mucosa and submucosa into the duodenal lumen like the finger of a glove [10], and are usually solitary. They must be distinguished from duodenal duplication, which involves all layers of the intestinal wall. Intraluminal DD arise from a partial duodenal diaphragm or web during early development (7th week) that gradually elongates over time due to the mechanical traction exerted by peristalsis. In 40% of cases, it is associated with other congenital malformations [5,10].

Duodenal diverticula are generally asymptomatic. Only 1-5% are symptomatic [3].

In the past, the presence of duodenal diverticulum was discovered through barium follow-through tests or upper endoscopy. Nowadays, the diagnosis is confirmed through abdominal CT scan, which is the first tool used to identify the diverticulum when gas, liquid or debris are found in its vicinity near the second part of the duodenum [5].

Duodenal diverticulum can be symptomatic, and express as haemorrhage, diverticulitis, jaundice, cholangitis, pancreatitis or even perforation [3].

The most common biliopancreatic complications are caused by the lithogenic mechanism of direct compression by the diverticulum on the common bile duct and the dysfunction of Oddi's sphincter [5]. Obstructive jaundice, known as Lemmel syndrome, can result from compression of the common bile duct due

to a periampullary duodenal diverticulum, in the absence of choledocholithiasis or a neoplasm [8]. Once diagnosed, management is straightforward and conservative, with recovery facilitated by antibiotics and hydration. No recurrence has been reported. In conclusion, acute obstructive pancreatitis secondary to duodenal diverticulitis is rare, with only five cases described in the literature to date. Physicians should consider duodenal diverticulitis in patients with a flare-up of pancreatitis who have a duodenal diverticulum. While radiological exams such as CT scan and/or MRI can facilitate diagnosis, it remains essential to exclude the presence of a tumour through other investigations [1].

Additionally, the presence of bacteria inside the diverticula that increase beta-glucuronidase has been recognized as a potential origin of idiopathic acute pancreatitis. In rare cases, papillary diverticulum can be associated with chronic pancreatitis [5].

The duodenal perforation is the rarest, but also the most dangerous complication with the highest mortality rate (ranging from 8 to 34%). It can be mainly caused by peptic digestive processes as a result of the retention of food in the diverticula forming a diverticulitis (62%). Other causes, such as ulcerations (5%), enterolithiasis (1%), blunt abdominal trauma (5%), or iatrogenic (5%) perforation during an ERCP, have also been described, spontaneous perforations are rare [3,7].

Conclusion

Duodenal diverticulum remains a diagnosis that should not be overlooked, given the number of the possible complications originating from it, especially pancreatitis. Accurate diagnosis requires a high level of clinical suspicion. This case report enhances the importance of considering the duodenal diverticulum as a potential etiology of a pancreatitis, despite its scarcity.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this case report.

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